

SourceData_Fig. 3abch

Rb-α-xCT

AB_xCT#07-11-22_Round5(20sec),8-8. scan_raw

Rb-α-Lipoyl (DLAT)

Rb-α-CD98

Rb-α-UQCRC2

Ms-α-SDHB

Rb-α-COX2

AB_xCT#07-11-22_Round1,3-3. scan_raw

Ms-α-IRP1

Ms-α-DLAT

Ms-α-NFS1

Rb-α-UQCRCFS1

AB_xCT#07-11-22_Round2,1-1. scan_raw

Rb-α-VDAC1

Rb-α-FECH

Ms-α-NDUFS8

AB_xCT#07-11-22_Round5 (20sec),5-5. scan_raw

AB_xCT#07-11-22_Round2, 12-12. scan_raw

Ms-α-TUBA

AB_xCT#07-11-22_Round5(10sec),4-4. scan_raw

Ms-α-NDUFV2

AB_xCT#07-11-22_Round3,5-5. scan_raw

Ms-α-NDUFS1

Ms-α-NDUFB6

AB_xCT#07-11-22_Round4,4-4. scan_raw

Ms-α-NDUFA9

Rb-α-NTHL1

Ms-α-NDUFA13

Rb-α-COX6A

AB_xCT#07-11-22_Round2, 3-3. scan_raw

AB_xCT#07-11-22_Round3, 12-12. scan_raw

AB_xCT#07-11-22_Round1,1-1. scan_raw

AB_xCT#07-11-22_Round4,10-10. scan_raw

AB_xCT#07-11-22_Round3,3-3. scan_raw

AB_xCT#17-10-22_Round1, 14-14. scan_raw

AB_xCT#07-11-22_Round1, 8-8. scan_raw

AB_xCT#07-11-22_Round4,16-16. scan_raw

AB_xCT#07-11-22_Round2, 8-8. scan_raw

AB_xCT#07-11-22_Round3, 22-22. scan_raw

AB_xCT#07-11-22_Round3, 22-22. scan_raw

AB_xCT#07-11-22_Round4, 5-5. scan_raw